

The challenges in colorectal peritoneal cancer care

De uitdagingen in de zorg voor patiënten met colorectale peritoneale
metastasen

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

door

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Chapter 4 – Systemic chemotherapy in addition to CRS-HIPEC for colorectal peritoneal metastases: a critical systematic review on the impact on overall survival

Table 1 – Search systematic review

Supplementary Table 1A – Search strategy PubMed		
	MeSH-term	Free search
#1 Colorectal carcinoma	Colorectal Neoplasms OR Colonic Neoplasms OR Rectal Neoplasms	Colorectal cancer OR Colorectal carcinoma OR Colon cancer OR Colon carcinoma OR Rectal cancer OR Rectal carcinoma OR Colorectal malignancies OR Colorectal neoplasia OR Colorectal neoplasm OR Rectal malignancies OR Rectal neoplasia OR Rectal neoplasm
#2 Peritoneal metastases		Peritoneal metastases OR Peritoneal metastasis OR Peritoneal carcinomatosis OR Peritoneum OR Carcinomatosis OR Peritoneal surface malignancies
#3 CRS-HIPEC	Cytoreduction Surgical Procedures OR Hyperthermic Intraperitoneal Chemotherapy	CRS OR Cytoreductive surgery OR Debulking OR Cytoreduction OR Hyperthermic intraperitoneal chemotherapy OR HIPEC OR Intraperitoneal chemotherapy
#4 Systemic therapy	Chemotherapy, Adjuvant OR Neoadjuvant Therapy	Perioperative chemotherapy OR Adjuvant chemotherapy OR Neoadjuvant chemotherapy OR Perioperative systemic therapy OR Adjuvant systemic therapy OR Neoadjuvant systemic therapy OR Systemic therapy OR Chemotherapy
#5 Outcomes	Survival OR Disease-Free Survival OR Survival Analysis	Survival OR Disease-free survival OR Survival analysis
Search: (#1 MeSH-term OR #1 Free search) AND (#2 MeSH-term OR #2 Free search) AND (#3 MeSH-term OR #3 Free search) AND (#4 MeSH-term OR #4 Free search) AND (#5 MeSH-term OR #5 Free search)		
Supplementary Table 1B – Search strategy Cochrane		
	MeSH-term	Free search
#1 Colorectal carcinoma	Colorectal Neoplasms OR Colonic Neoplasms OR Rectal Neoplasms	Colorectal cancer OR Colorectal carcinoma OR Colon cancer OR Colon carcinoma OR Rectal cancer OR Rectal carcinoma OR Colorectal malignancies OR Colorectal neoplasia OR Colorectal neoplasm OR Rectal malignancies OR Rectal neoplasia OR Rectal neoplasm
#2 Peritoneal metastases		Peritoneal metastases OR Peritoneal metastasis OR Peritoneal carcinomatosis OR Peritoneum OR Carcinomatosis OR Peritoneal surface malignancies
#3 CRS-HIPEC	Cytoreduction Surgical Procedures OR Hyperthermic Intraperitoneal Chemotherapy	CRS OR Cytoreductive surgery OR Debulking OR Cytoreduction OR Hyperthermic intraperitoneal chemotherapy OR HIPEC OR Intraperitoneal chemotherapy

#4 Systemic therapy	Chemotherapy, Adjuvant	Perioperative chemotherapy OR Adjuvant chemotherapy OR Neoadjuvant chemotherapy OR Perioperative systemic therapy OR Adjuvant systemic therapy OR Neoadjuvant systemic therapy OR Systemic therapy OR Chemotherapy
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#5 Outcomes	Survival OR Disease-Free Survival OR Survival Analysis	Survival OR Disease-free survival OR Survival analysis OR overall survival
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Search: (#1 MeSH-term OR #1 Free search) AND (#2 MeSH-term OR #2 Free search) AND (#3 MeSH-term OR #3 Free search) AND (#4 MeSH-term OR #4 Free search) AND (#5 MeSH-term OR #5 Free search)

Supplementary Table 1C – Search strategy EMBASE

	MeSH-term	Free search
#1 Colorectal carcinoma		Colorectal tumour OR Colon tumour OR Rectum tumour OR Colorectal cancer OR Colorectal carcinoma OR Colon cancer OR Colon carcinoma OR Rectum cancer OR Rectum carcinoma
#2 Peritoneal metastases		Peritoneum metastasis OR Carcinomatous peritonitis OR Peritoneum OR Carcinomatosis OR Peritoneum cancer
#3 CRS-HIPEC		Cytoreductive surgery OR Hyperthermic intraperitoneal chemotherapy OR Debulking OR Cytoreduction OR Intraperitoneal chemotherapy
#4 Systemic therapy		Adjuvant chemotherapy OR Neoadjuvant chemotherapy OR Neoadjuvant therapy OR Perioperative chemotherapy OR Perioperative systemic therapy OR Adjuvant systemic therapy OR neoadjuvant systemic therapy OR Systemic therapy OR Chemotherapy OR Cancer chemotherapy
#5 Outcomes		Survival OR Survival rate OR Disease-free survival OR Overall survival OR Survival analysis

Search: #1 Free search AND #2 Free search AND #3 Free search AND #4 Free search AND #5 Free search)

Chapter 10 – Absolute bioavailability of oxaliplatin following intraperitoneal administration by electrostatic pressurized intraperitoneal aerosol chemotherapy (ePIPAC): systemic pharmacokinetics of the CRC-PIPAC-II trial

Chapter 10 Appendix Table 1 – Table on all patient characteristics (adapted from Rauwerdink et al (2024) [14])

ID	Sex	Age (years)	Primary tumour location	Histology	Onset of PM	Time diagnosis PM to (weeks)	
						Enrolment	First ST
1	Male	41	Ascending colon	AC	Metachronous	5	8
2	Male	54	Appendix	LAMN ^a	Synchronous	5	6
3	Female	70	Transverse colon	AC-SRC	Synchronous	7	10
4	Male	61	Ascending colon	MAC	Synchronous	3	4
5	Female	62	Appendix	AC	Synchronous	3	5
6	Male	54	Ascending colon	MAC	Synchronous	3	6
7	Male	57	Transverse colon	MAC	Metachronous	3	5
8	Female	68	Caecum	AC	Synchronous	5	7
9	Female	45	Appendix	GCC	Synchronous	4	5
10	Female	69	Appendix	MAC	Synchronous	6	8
11	Female	59	Caecum	MAC	Synchronous	1	2
12	Male	54	Sigmoid	MAC	Synchronous	3	5
13	Female	64	Appendix	AC-SRC	Synchronous	4	6
14	Male	54	Appendix	Unknown ^b	Synchronous	5	7
15	Female	43	Appendix	MAC-SRC	Synchronous	8	9
16	Male	70	Ascending colon	MAC	Metachronous	6	8
17	Female	47	Sigmoid	AC	Synchronous	3	4
18	Female	45	Appendix	AC	Synchronous	8	9

This figure was adapted from Rauwerdink et al (2024) [13].

PM peritoneal metastases; ST systemic therapy; AC adenocarcinoma; LAMN low-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasm; SRC signet ring cell; MAC mucinous adenocarcinoma; GCC Goblet Cell (adeno)carcinoma.

^a Histopathological assessment of resected specimens unexpectedly revealed low-grade pseudomyxoma peritonei originating of a low-grade appendiceal mucinous neoplasm.

^b Reviewed histopathology and unexpected diagnosis of high-grade pseudomyxoma peritonei originating from primary tumour of unknown histologic grade (in situ).

Chapter 10 Appendix Table 2 – Overview of outcomes of C_{max} and corresponding T_{max} for systemic administration and PIPAC

ID	C _{max} total after systemic (ug/mL)	Time to C _{max} total after systemic (minutes)	C _{max} UF after systemic (ug/mL)	Time to C _{max} UF after systemic (minutes)	C _{max} total after PIPAC (ug/mL)	Time to C _{max} total after PIPAC (minutes)	C _{max} UF after PIPAC (ug/mL)	Time to C _{max} UF after PIPAC (minutes)
1	5.99	120	3.41	120	2.27	80	1.84	30
2	7.16	123	3.53	123	2.51	80	1.37	80
3	9.96	120	3.91	120	2.45	9735	0.88	65
4	7.70	120	3.90	120	2.81	85	1.74	30
5	10.41	120	3.67	120	3.67	70	2.13	70
6	5.41	120	2.28	120	3.00	120	1.42	30
7	8.59	120	3.12	124	3.14	145	1.45	40
8	8.51	120	3.92	120	3.58	60	1.37	30
9	11.55	120	5.88	120	2.31	130	1.05	65
10	7.45	120	3.28	120	3.62	72	1.25	72
11	2.24	127	1.35	127	2.60	163	0.72	53
12	7.48	135	2.64	135	3.12	212	1.48	107
13	9.07	124	3.88	64	5.19	66	2.58	66
14	8.32	123	2.84	65	2.58	86	N/A	N/A
15	6.43	127	2.57	65	3.40	85	2.32	45
16	7.46	125	3.94	125	3.41	67	1.72	67
17	4.80	134	1.06	38	3.92	81	1.41	81
18	7.69	130	3.48	130	2.93	125	2.14	35
Median (IQR)	7.6 (6.3 – 8.7)	122 (120 – 127)	3.4 (2.6 – 3.9)	120 (106 – 124)	3.6 (2.6 – 3.1)	85 (72 – 134)	1.5 (1.3 – 2.0)	65 (33 – 71)

Chapter 10 Appendix Table 3 – Population Pharmacokinetic parameters of the final model

	Mean value	RSE (%)	Shrinkage (%)
CL (L/hour)	1.44	6.7	
V ₂ (L)	31	12.1	
Ka (/hour)	1.93	Fixed	
Q (L/hour)	20,4.	11.2	
V3 (L)	150	9.2	
F	0.477	9.9	
Bmax (μmol/L)	0.95	Fixed	
AlbBmax	0.0798	10.7	
Kd (μmol/L)	0.0633	Fixed	
Interindividual variability (IIV)			
CL (CV%)	13	19.9	3
V2 (CV%)	53.2	15	3
CL~V2 (CV%)	101.1%		
Ka (CV%)	114.9	19	18
F (CV%)	26.7	29	16
Bmax (CV%)	17.5	20	20
Random residual variability			
Unbound Proportional (%)	17.3	23	13
Bound Proportional (%)	23.8	20	5
Unbound Additive (ug/mL)	0.1	29	13
Bound Additive (ug/mL)	0.2	30	5

RSE=relative standard error, CL=clearance, V2=volume of distribution central compartment, Q= inter compartmental clearance, V3=volume of distribution of peripheral compartment, F= Bioavailability, Bmax=maximum binding capacity, AlbMax = impact of albumin on Bmax, Kd is the equilibrium dissociation constant., CV%=percentage coefficient of variation.